

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: WU

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“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report – Netherlands

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Main authors	
Name	Organisation
Liesbeth Dries	WU

Quality reviewers	
Name	Organisation
George Malliopoulos, Eirini Efthymiadou	Q-PLAN

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of WU for the organisation and validation of the culinary event in the Netherlands on 28/03/2023. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the culinary event in the Netherlands;
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event;
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

A culinary event was organized in the Netherlands on 28 March 2023. For this event, a cooperation was sought with a local caterer / restaurant owner. The caterer (Hutten, <https://www.hutten.eu/business-horeca/contact>) is experienced with working with local products. Apart from the local dimension of the food produced, the caterer is also concerned with the broader perspective on sustainable food production and supports initiatives that target food waste reduction. The concept selection and activities were done in collaboration with the caterer (including the focus of the culinary event on local ingredients and food products, as well as sustainable food production more generally). Table 1 shows the timeframe in which the culinary event was organized.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Welcome and introduction of event	A short welcome was provided by the organizer to the participants, introducing the agroBRIDGES project and the chef who prepared the food	12:30 – 12:45	Omnia building, Wageningen, the Netherlands
Food presentation and tasting	Different dishes were presented, each using local agri-food products in an innovative way.	12:45 – 14:00	Omnia building, Wageningen, the Netherlands

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The location for the event was chosen in collaboration with the caterer. The choice was made for the reception area of the Omnia building on Wageningen University campus. Omnia is a new building where a lot of receptions and events are organized. The preference of the caterer was motivated by the presence of a professional kitchen where the food products can be prepared. The caterer has used this venue before as it also houses the faculty club restaurant of the university. Figures 1 and 2 show pictures of the reception area at Omnia. The pictures show that this is very open area with a lot of natural light.

The timing of the event was based on the availability of the caterer and especially also the venue. The timeline of the event organization was as follows: (i) contacting the caterer and discussing possibilities and ideas for local food-based culinary event; (ii) reservation of the venue; (iii) inviting participants with deadline for registration because the caterer needed to know the number of people at the event; (iv) preparing materials for promotion during the event; (v) event.

Figure 1: Event venue, stairs to the reception area at Omnia

Figure 2: Event venue, view of the reception area at Omnia

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

Table 2 provides an overview of the personnel involved in the organisation of the event. The main roles were fulfilled by the organizer and the catering manager. The chef played an important role in the design of the food that was prepared, using local food ingredients.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Event organizer	1	Providing suggestions for suitable events and collaborators	External	N/A
Catering manager	1	Execution of agreements about food, event, promotion and information materials during the event, and administration	External	N/A
Chef	1	Design and preparation of food for guests	External	N/A
Waiter	2	Taking care of food and drinks for guests during event	External	N/A
Kitchen personnel	2	Preparing food for guests	External	N/A
Organizer	2	Design event; discussion and agreement with caterer about food; agreement with caterer about promotion; invitations to participants; follow-up with participants and caterer	Internal	4 person days
Administrator	1	Administrative arrangements with catering manager	Internal	1 person day

2.4 Event material

Promotion and information material was used at the event to inform participants about the specific origin of the food that was offered to them. These promotion materials included information (in both Dutch and English) and the logo of the agroBRIDGES project. Figure 3 shows an example of a leaflet that was used for promotion.

Figure 3: Example of the promotion material that was used during the event

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

The main contributors to the event were the caterer and the manager of the venue. First, a meeting was held with an event organizer who works at Food Valley NL (<https://www.foodvalley.nl/>). Food Valley NL is an organisation that works together with businesses and other partners to accelerate the transition to a sustainable food system. The person at Food Valley provided suggestions for possible events that could be organized as well as suggestions for collaborators for such an event. The meeting with Food Valley was established more than one month before the event. Based on the suggestions, the choice was made for a culinary event together with one of the catering companies that Food Valley had worked with on other occasions.

Next, the caterer was contacted (about one month prior to the event) because the food products would play a central role in the event. Together with the caterer, the purpose of the event, possibilities for focusing on local food products in the event and the practical organization of the event were discussed.

After this discussion, the organizer contacted the venue manager to agree on the timing and location of the event. At the same time, the catering manager discussed with the chef to decide on specific products that could be offered during the event. A suggestion for food tastings was then proposed to the organizer and an agreement was made about the location and the total cost of the event. An initial estimate of the number of participants was made to the venue organizer (not to exceed the capacity of the venue) and the caterer at this point. This number was confirmed about 3 working days before the actual event.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

Invitations were made by email to staff and (senior) student members at Wageningen University. This was deemed an appropriate target audience because of the focus on local food products. Wageningen is a small city, and the majority of its population is affiliated with the university. Furthermore, some innovative food products, using local ingredients, have been developed in Wageningen (by university students), some of which are now reproduced by the catering company and the chefs that we cooperated with in the event. Given the capacity of the venue, the need to know the number of participants in the event to prepare a sufficient number of food items, and the cost of the event, invitations were not open but send out in a targeted way until spaces at the event were filled. Invitations were sent out 3 weeks before the event and confirmation from participants was required one week before the event.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

The event was a culinary event where a chef prepared special food products that used local and sustainable ingredients. For each food item, an information leaflet was provided, providing specific information about the food, its ingredients and the story behind this, and also advertising the agroBRIDGES project by use of its logo. Examples of the food products, pictures of the food, the information leaflets and the event are provided below and in figures 4 to 9.

- Krenkelaar (Fig. 5). This sparkling cider is made from apples from the Betuwe region (the region around Wageningen). Apart from using local ingredients, the cider also helps to reduce food waste because the apples that are used in the cider are outside of the class A apples that are sold in supermarkets. Profits that are made with this product are used to sow flowerbeds for wild bees.
- Thijsthee, fruit drink (Fig. 6). Thijs drinks are developed in a mission against food waste and use fruit that cannot be sold through regular channels and would otherwise be destroyed.
- Beekrider, a local fish alternative for salmon (Fig. 7). Streekvis is a fish farm in the Betuwe region (the region around Wageningen) where fish is being produced in a sustainable way. One type of fish that they produce is the Beekrider. This fish has a similar texture, look and taste to salmon and was used by the chef in a snack as a sustainable alternative to salmon.
- Beenbean (Fig. 8) is a company that processes locally produced beans in bean products. In the event, Tempeh was made and served as an appealing snack with local ingredients.
- Zwamcijsje (Fig. 9) is a product that was developed by Wageningen students and the recipe is now used by the catering company that we worked with. The snack is a sustainable alternative to the traditional sausage roll (a popular snack in the Netherlands). Instead of the traditional meat filling, the Zwamcijsje has a filling based on locally produced mushrooms

Figure 4: Culinary event

Figure 5: Krenkelaar, sparkling apple cider

Figure 6: Thijsthee, fruit drink

Figure 7: Beekrider, local alternative to salmon

Figure 8: BeenBean, Tempeh from locally grown beans

Figure 9: Zwamcijsje, local, veggie alternative to a sausage roll

3.2 Event participation

Table 3 reports on the number of participants in the event. The total number of participants was 29.

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Organizer	1
Collaborators (caterer, restaurant, venue)	3
Consumers	25
Total	29

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Validation forms were filled in only by the consumers / participants to the event, and this only partially. In total, 10 feedback questionnaires were filled.

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Q1. Familiar with SFSC?	8		2		0	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Q2. Event informative about new types of food in region?	2	6	1	0	0	1
Q3. Event helpful to know local business / restaurants + their efforts for local food?	2	5	2	0	0	1
Q4. Activities helpful to understand value of local food, recipes and benefits?*	2	3	4	1	0	0
Q5. Enough info about finding restaurants / kitchens?	2	3	5	0	0	0
Total						
Question	>monthly	3-4 times/yr	Twice/yr	Once/yr	Never	No answer
Q6. Like similar events being organized? How often?	1	1	4	4	0	0

* Note that the focus of the information leaflets was targeting the sustainability benefits of the food that was offered, but not the health benefits. The latter were therefore not asked for explicitly in the questionnaire.

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The event concept is very broad and can be relevant also for my organization. What I adjusted to the particular local conditions was to more explicitly bring in the focus on environmental benefits of the food

choices made (sustainable, combatting food waste, vegetarian alternatives) because the SFSC focus in itself is not sufficiently interesting or innovative here. In addition, it should be noted that the event was costly (the caterer, the chef, the venue had to be paid for their services). The concept could point this out.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Maybe. I liked learning about the sustainable and local food solutions that were being offered by the caterer and in the restaurants that the caterer works with so if I ever have to organize something similar in the future, I will work with the same collaborators. I don't foresee any adjustments.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

More than sufficient.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Detailed enough.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

Event organization is not the organising partner's core business (far from it) and events are generally outsourced to external partners, or other entities in our organisation. However, these specialized event organizers have their own procedures, templates and timelines. Since the purpose of this task was to try out the agroBRIDGES event tools (templates, etc.), and since the budget did not foresee outsourcing of the event organization to specialized entities, the organising partner tried to do this. Limitations occurred in the limited knowledge of potential collaborators, lack of experience with event organization and a lack of networks of potential participants. For these reasons, much time was spent in gathering knowledge through discussions with experts and some specific choices were made such as the target group of participants being university staff rather than 'the general public'. Also, the budget implications of using a caterer who created special food snacks made that the number of participants was limited. Finally, with Wageningen University well-known for research on sustainable food systems and solutions, the choice had to be made to not only advertise local provenance of the food ingredients, but also broader sustainability implications of the food offered (such as vegetarian alternatives and food waste reducing choices).

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Flexible enough